

ESTIMATION OF BISMUTH. PART IV. MICRO-ANALYSIS WITH PHENYLARSONIC ACID

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A micro determination of bismuth, gravimetrically with phenylarsonic acid in presence of Ag, Hg (*ic*), Pb, Cu, Cd, Co, Ni Th (*ous*), alkalis, alkaline earths and sulphate ions, has been described.

The procedures are similar to those used in parts I and III of this series

In Parts I and III of this series, (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 119, 187) it has been shown by the author that macro-quantities of bismuth can be estimated gravimetrically and volumetrically with the reagent phenylarsonic acid and separated from silver, copper, cadmium, cobalt, nickel, mercury (*ic*), lead, zirconium, thorium, tin, alkalis, alkaline earths (*e.g.*, Ca, Sr, Ba and Mg), thallium (*ous*) and sulphate ions.

The present paper deals with the estimation of small quantities of bismuth and its separation from copper, cadmium, cobalt, nickel, silver, mercury (*ic*), lead, alkalis, alkaline earths, thallium (*ous*) and sulphate ions.

During this investigation it has been found that the bismuth precipitate, obtained in presence of ammonium acetate, is of more crystalline character than what is obtained in presence of sodium acetate.

Bismuth is precipitated in a micro-beaker and by means of Emich's asbestos packed filter-stick, the filtration and washings are carried out. The beaker and the filter-stick containing the precipitate are dried in Benedetti-Pichler's drying apparatus in a current of dry air and weighed in a Kuhlmann's balance.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The reagents and the standard solutions, used during this investigation, are exactly the same as were used earlier (Parts I and III of this series), except that instead of 10% solution of sodium or ammonium acetate, 20% solutions are used and that the bismuth nitrate solution, prepared from 'reagent quality' subnitrate and standardised in the same way as referred to in Parts I and III, containing only 0.997 mg. of bismuth per c.c., is taken.

Procedure.—During the micro-estimations almost the same procedures are followed as were described for the macro-method (*loc. cit.*).

For the estimation of bismuth, a measured quantity of the bismuth nitrate solution (containing just sufficient nitric acid to keep the bismuth in solution), from a micro-burette, was taken in a micro-beaker. To this solution were added 1 c.c. of the reagent solution (1% in water) and a few c.c. (2 to 3 c.c.) of the sodium acetate solution (20% in water) or after the addition of the reagent, the solution was just neutralised with dilute 2*N*-ammonia (using a drop of Wesselow's indicator), acidified with acetic acid (2*N*), 2 to 4 drops of which were added in excess and treated with 1 c.c. of ammonium acetate solution (20% in water). The solution was then diluted to 6-7 c.c. and heated for about 10 to 15 minutes in its stand on the boiling water-bath till the precipitate became crystalline. The precipitate was allowed to settle and collect at one side of the beaker. The supernatant solution was then drawn off through the asbestos-mat filter-stick and the precipitate was sucked as dry as possible. It was washed four to five times using 3 to 4 c.c. of hot water each time. The beaker with the precipitate and the filter-stick was first heated on the water-bath for about 10 minutes to remove all the adhering water and then finally dried for 20 minutes in a current of dry air at 100° in a Benedetti-Pichler's drying apparatus. The beaker with the precipitate and the filter-stick was then weighed in the micro-

balance after taking the usual precautions of wiping with moist flannel and dry chamois respectively, as prescribed for micro-methods.

The amount of bismuth was found by multiplying the weight of the bismuth compound with the factor 0.4906. Some of the results appear in Table I.

TABLE I

Wt. of Bi- Complex. Bi found.			Wt. of Bi- Complex. Bi found.			Wt. of Bi- Complex. Bi found.		
In presence of sodium acetate			In presence of am. acetate			In presence of am. acetate.		
0.997 mg.	2.023 mg.	0.992 mg.	1.545	3.137	1.539	2.642	5.411	2.655
0.997 mg.	2.030 mg.	0.996 mg.	1.097	2.227	1.093	2.094	4.307	2.109
1.097 mg.	2.228 mg.	1.093 mg.	0.598	1.210	0.594			
0.997	2.028	0.995						

If thallium (ous), alkalis and alkaline earth salts (*e.g.*, salts of Ca, Sr, Ba and Mg) are present in the solution, they do not interfere with the estimation of bismuth by the procedure given above.

It must be noted that large excess of sodium or ammonium acetate or prolonged boiling with excess of sodium or ammonium acetate leads to low results.

Estimation of Bismuth in presence of Sulphate ions.—To the solution, containing a few drops of dilute nitric acid in excess to keep the sulphate in solution, was added 1 c.c. of the reagent solution. If any precipitate appears, that should be dissolved with a few drops of dilute nitric acid and warming on the water-bath. The solution was then neutralised with dilute 2*N* ammonia (using a drop of Wesselow's indicator), acidified with acetic acid (2*N*), added 2 to 4 drops of acetic acid (2*N*) in excess, 1 c.c. of ammonium acetate solution and proceeded as usual. Results are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Bi taken	Sodium sulphate taken	Bi found	Bi taken	Sodium sulphate taken	Bi found
0.997 mg.	10.0 mg.	0.994 mg.	1.097 mg.	10.0 mg.	1.10 mg.

Estimation of Bismuth in presence of Copper, Cadmium, Silver, Cobalt and Nickel.—The nitrate solution, after the addition of 1 c.c. of the reagent, was neutralised with dilute 2*N*-ammonia. A few crystals of potassium cyanide (reagent quality), sufficient to keep the interfering cations in solution, were then added, the solution acidified with 2*N* acetic acid solution (with a drop of Wesselow's indicator), 4 drops of acetic acid (2*N*) then added in excess along with 0.5 c.c. of the ammonium acetate solution, diluted to 6-7 c.c. and the usual procedure followed. Results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Bi taken.	Other metals taken.	Bi found.	Bi taken.	Other metals taken.	Bi found.	Bi taken.	Other metals taken.	Bi found.
0.997 mg	Cu 10.35	0.992 mg	1.097 mg	Cu 10.35	1.106 mg	1.296 mg	Cd 7.189	1.289 mg
1.097	Cd 7.189	1.091	0.997	Ag 10.61	0.994	0.997	Ag 10.61	0.991
0.997	Co 10.32	1.001	1.097	Co 10.32	1.099	1.097	Ni 12.06	1.104
0.997	Ni 12.06	1.001						

Estimation of Bismuth in presence of Lead.—In presence of lead, bismuth was estimated by the method followed for the individual estimation of it in presence of acetic acid buffered

with ammonium acetate except that after acidification of the solution with dilute acetic acid (2*N*) and addition of 4 drops of the acetic acid (2*N*) in excess, the solution was diluted to 6 c.c. and heated for some time on the water-bath with the addition of 0.5 c.c. of the ammonium acetate solution. If the precipitate was not crystalline, further quantities of the ammonium acetate solution, 0.5 c.c. each time, should be added and heated till the precipitate became so. The precipitate was then allowed to settle and treated as usual. Some of the results appear in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Taken. Ammonium acetate soln. Bi found.			Taken. Ammonium acetate soln. Bi found.				
Bismuth	1.047mg.	1 c.c.	1.052mg.	Bismuth	1.106mg.	1 c.c.	1.202mg.
Lead	14.24			Lead	7.12		

Estimation of Bismuth in presence of Mercury (ic).—To the nitrate solution (containing a little free nitric acid) was added 1 c.c. of the reagent and diluted to about 6 c.c., 0.5 c.c. of the ammonium acetate solution were then added and heated on a water-bath for some time. If the precipitate be not crystalline further portions of the ammonium acetate solution (0.5 c.c. each time) should be added and heated till the precipitate becomes crystalline. The precipitate was then allowed to settle and the usual procedure followed. Results as shown in Table V.

TABLE V

Taken Ammonium acetate soln. Bi found.			Taken. Ammonium acetate soln. Bi found.				
Bismuth	0.997mg.	1 c.c.	0.998mg.	Bismuth	0.997	1 c.c.	0.994
Mercury	10.06			Mercury	10.06		

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